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A FRAMEWORK FOR EXPLORATION PHASE OF EXPERIENCE DESIGN AND A CASE STUDY IN LIGHTING DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

Despite apparent benefits of Experience Sampling (ES) for experience design and research, it has been scarcely used in the field. Among the reasons, the conventional ES uses generic questions which are often irrelevant to the context of ES in the form of open-end questions demanding minutes of time to respond. Likewise, its subjective and ununiformed qualitative data are difficult to apply for practical design guide. As to these issues, the present paper suggests an adapted ES, 'Context-Specific Experience Sampling' which incorporates a small scale user-experience data process prior to the actual conduct of ES. The preparation process consists of experience 'pooling', 'sorting', and 'extracting' phases to generate pertinent and effective experience keywords for ES. The present paper explains in detail the structure and procedure of the proposed method with case examples from a small scale lighting experience study for offices and dress shops.

Keywords: Experience Design, Experience Sampling Method, Lighting Design

INTRODUCTION

Understanding experience values of human stakeholders and identifying the key drivers for such experience values form the core capability needed in experience design. This paper presents a framework for understanding and identifying context-specific user experience values in the form of thematic keywords which applies for effective experience sampling method.

Experience Sampling Method (ESM) refers to a set of techniques for collecting information about people's

behaviors, thoughts or feelings in the context and content of the daily life (Hektner, Schmidt & Csikszentmihalyi, 2007). In the usual application of ESM, participants deliver self-reports or answer to structured questions at certain regular times, or receive randomly sent electronic signals during the study period. The unique contribution of this method is that researchers can obtain data on real-time experiences as they occur in natural settings (Scollon, Kim-Pieto & Diener, 2003).

Despite the benefits of ESM, there are few research cases discussing application of ESM in the field of experience design, main philosophy of which emphasizes importance of understanding the context for the designed experience.

Although investigation of context for experience design is recognized as critical (Cardelo & Wise, 2008), there has been a lack of reliable and pragmatic methodological framework enabling researchers to systematically incorporate contextual information into the investigation of user experiences.

Despite many apparent benefits for experience design, ESM as a practical tool in design process has been limited because of several shortcomings of the method. Conventional ESM is not capable of rigorously investigating participant's contexts and activities whereas it simply casts questions about the participants' context information without objective means of gathering such information. There is a need for ESM framework to rigorously collect contextual data via an objective method, encompassing pertinent experience measures which enable participants to quickly and pertinently answer, and supporting ease of objective and comparable data

generation and application across settings and contexts.

To address these issues, we have developed a conceptual framework entitled, Context Specific Experience Sampling as an adapted ESM. The present paper explains the developed framework and also illustrates its application with case examples from a small scale lighting design study conducted for offices and dress shops. The Context-Specific Experience Sampling method is composed of three phases before actual conduct of ES: experience polling, sorting, and extracting.

CONTEXT-SPECIFIC EXPERIENCE SAMPLING FRAMEWORK

EXPERIENCE POOLING

As shown in the diagram below, 'experience pooling' within the experience processing framework is aimed at gathering diverse user experience data via such techniques as GT (Generative Techniques) and ECA (Experience Cut-in Analysis). It is eventually to extract context-specific evaluative experience themes from the data pool and thus apply for the subsequent ES (Experience Sampling). The explanations about the application of GT and ECA follow.

Figure 1. Context-specific experience sampling framework

Generative Techniques

Generative Tools (Visser, Stappers, der Lugt & Sanders, 2005) is one of the generative techniques which have been developed in the design research to extract insights from depths of the consumers' mind. It is based on the philosophy that people's thoughts, feelings, dreams and new ideas can be better explored when they actually say, do, and make (Kim, 2009). A key strength of GT comes from the fact that GT is future-oriented in a way to reveal the needs and wishes for new experiences as well as ideas, whereas the conventional user study techniques (interviews, observations and focus groups) generally focus on uncovering explicit and observable

knowledge about contexts offering a view of people's current and past experience.

As for office lighting design research, 14 office users of the age between 20 and 40 were invited to the study. As for the shop lighting environment, 9 women of 30-40 ages were selected as they are considered as the most active consumers. The participants were initially contacted and provided a brief orientation about the study and participation process. The orientation took place face-to-face or via telephone conversation. The materials needed for the subsequent sensitizing activity were prepared and posted to the participants after the orientation. During the orientation, participants were also informed of the instructions of workbook use and the subsequent interview.

Figure 2. Workbook for experience sensitizing: A-Workbook, B-Collage material, C-3D modeling material

Sensitizing stage is designed to provide participants with a period of thinking and looking over his/her own office lighting environments, in the case of office lighting study, and the dress shops the participants often visit. For several days, participants were given tasks by the workbook. The tasks are for example asking them to draw or photograph the lighting environments of the target settings with some descriptions of the environmental features, activities or events. Polaroid camera was provided for them to take photos which were then attach to the workbook. The participants were requested to bring the workbook to the main GT session.

This sensitizing stage was assumed to enable the participants to consciously think about the target environments and their experiences and thus leads to an effective GT sessions for the visual presentation of their experiences through the prepared materials. During the main session, participants were asked to think about and express their needs and wishes through the collage and 3D modeling. Researchers

collected and reviewed the workbook before individual interview. Figure 3 shows the collage and 3D modeling examples produced by the participants for their ideal office lighting environments and dress shop. Each participant was asked to explain his/her work. The sessions were audio and video recorded for transcripts.

Figure 3. Example photos of collage and 3D modeling: A-for office lighting, B-for dress shop

Experience Cut-In Analysis (ECA)

Borrowing the term ‘cut-in’ from the film industry, Experience Cut-In Analysis is a method of interview in which interviewer and participants have a discourse over the cut-in photos from the recorded video or taken photos from their daily life settings. In the present case, the photos from the GT workbook were used. The cut-in photos are the experience cut-ins of the participants in his/her own real life context. Having discourse over the cut-in photos, an interviewer asks structured or open questions to systematically explore the participants’ direct or related past experiences as for the lighting environments.

Figure 4. Example photos for Experience Cut-in Analysis

Under the present framework, ECA is designed as a tool to collect information of user’s past experiences

while GT focuses on the experiences that a user wishes to have in future. ECA enables a context based discourse over the participant’s experiences. ECA took place during the individual interview before the main GT sessions. Figure 4 shows example photos for ECA interviews taken from the recorded video in the case of office lighting study and photos of dress shops. ECA was designed to explore the participants’ past experiences while GT was for their future wishes and requirements.

EXPERIENCE SORTING

For design strategy of Product-Service Systems (PSS) composed of tightly integrated product and service elements to provide a total solution for human needs and wants, the E3 value concept has been proposed in which Experience Value (EV) structure (cf. Holbrook, 1999; Sheth, Newman & Gross, 1991) was incorporated in order to explore the product/service user experiences and their related values (Cho, Kim & Lee, 2010). Researchers utilized the EV concept and framework for the systematic experience sorting task over the data pooled from the GT. The experience value structure consists of four main dimensions which are functional, social, epistemic and emotional, where the latter is further classified into active and reactive emotional values similarly to the utilitarian and aesthetic emotions respectively of Scherer (Cho, Kim & Lee, 2010). The usefulness of applying E3 values in sorting contextual experiences is the E3 values structure guide allowing researcher to systematically classify the large number of ‘experience values’ using experience keywords pooled from GT.

Figure 5. E3 - Experience value structure

EXPERIENCE THEME EXTRACTION

Based on the classified experience keywords from the pool of experience data generated by GT and ECA, a set of experience themes were extracted

according to the five E3 Value dimensions. The extracted experience themes are for the eventual use in ES as the thematic keywords are applied to evaluate the users' own office lighting environments in the case of an office or dress shop lighting conditions. Table 1 presents the final extraction of the experience thematic keywords. The table enables to compare and contrast the experience themes between the office and shop environments.

	Office	Dress Shop
Functional	Clearness, Task Concentration, Work efficiency, Control, Convenient	Help-to-focus, Compatible-with
Social	Privacy	Making-me-pretty, Luxurious
Active Emotion	Comfortable, Energetic, Fun	Cozy, Easy, Interesting, Happy, Lively, Comfortable, Pleasant, Fun
Reactive Emotion	Vivid, Colorful, Soft Warm, Plain, Natural	Refreshing, Colorful, Splendid, Soft, Vivid, Tender, Modern, Harmonious, Bright, Delicate, Natural, Simple, Elegant, Neat, Clear
Epistemic	Novelty, Diversity	Novelty, Diversity,

Table 1. Experience themes extracted for Experience Sampling

A most noticeable difference between the office and shop environments resides on the comparison of the emotional experiences the users expect from the settings. Users expect diverse and rich emotional experiences in the shopping environment whereas they require more functional aspects of lighting in the office with fewer emotional experience needs. As for the functional experience values in the shopping environment, the keyword 'help-to-focus' means users wants the lighting to help to easily focus on the clothes while looking around and 'compatible-with' means compatible lighting ambience with the clothes. Such requirements as 'something new', 'different from others', and diverse lighting features and colors were sorted for the themes of novelty and

diversity which were both present for the office and shop environments.

EXPERIENCE SAMPLING

The purpose of context-specific experience sampling method is to evaluate the experience themes as participants are engaged in their relevant activities so that least amount of intervention is involved. In this way, the more truthful experiences are sampled with the embedded contextual information from which pertinent experiential implications for the lighting design could be extracted. Small tablet PCs such as Galaxy tabs can be used to present the questions in various forms while simultaneously turned-on audio and video recording functions at the time of ES. In figure 5, a wheel-form keyword display is illustrated for the participants to check their experience states according to the selectively presented experience theme words from the keyword set. The data is stored into the PC which would be retrieved later for experience analysis with the accompanied video and audio recordings for any further contextual analysis.

Figure 5. Experience Sampling: A-Office, B-Dress shop

CONCLUSION

The present paper has illustrated an adapted experience sampling framework, entitled 'Context-Specific Experience Sampling' with case examples from a small scale lighting research in the context of office and shop. A key benefit of the proposed ES model is believed to be the context-based and context-specific experience value themes - from the

pooling, sorting and extracting phases for ES questions. The information process comprising divergent to convergent approaches to user experiences enables a researcher to generate pertinent and efficient evaluative experience value keywords for effective ES. Another key contribution comes from the use of experience value structure for a theory-guided experience keyword sorting processes. The tablet-pc ES can help to integrate the video/audio-recorded information for further contextual analysis.

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